

SOCIAL SCIENCES

RISK FACTORS FOR SOCIALLY SIGNIFICANT DISEASES' ONSET

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ABSTRACT

Among the risk factors for the occurrence of socially significant diseases, highest attention is paid to arterial hypertension, the consumption of tobacco products, low physical activity, unhealthy diet, low consumption of fruit and vegetables, alcohol misuse and obesity. **The purpose** of the present research is to study the way of life and behaviour of group of people, in order to mitigate and prevent risk factors for the occurrence of socially significant diseases. We have implemented the following **methods**: documentary method for surveying the accessible documentation concerning the issue, sociological method and graphic method for result visualization. Via direct anonymous inquiry we have searched the opinion of 81 women and men – smokers at various ages concerning their dietary habits and behaviour. **The results** demonstrate that most respondents do not consume sufficient quantity of fruit and vegetables, yet more than 1/3 of them are training to stay healthy at least once weekly. **Conclusion**: as a result of the research we arrived to the conclusion that we need to elaborate programs for prevention and promotion of anti-risk behaviour of young people, health schools – seminars with teachers on psycho-hygienic, dietary and physical habits of children. Many socially significant diseases could be prevented with effective approaches for smoking and alcohol consumption control, healthy diet and physical activity.

Keywords: socially significant diseases, chronic non-communicable diseases, risk factors, World Health Organization (WHO).

1. Introduction

Socially significant diseases are the main reason for death cases and disability worldwide. According to the data provided by the WHO, these are the reasons behind the death of 41 million people annually which makes up 71% of all death cases. [10]

The mitigation of severity of chronic non-communicable diseases requires comprehensive approach and coping with the lack of equal footing in terms of healthcare in all areas. What is essential is the fact that health promotion and disease prophylactics could result in decreasing this severity with 70%. [8]

Forecasts of frequency and severity of socially significant diseases outline negative trend of increase, whereas according to our expectations their number would go up to 50 million thus questioning the achievement of Sustainable development goals and the goals set in advance for relative reduction of preterm death due to socially significant diseases with 25% until 2025. According to the analyses presented by the Ministry of Health, circulatory diseases are the leading reason within the lethal cases structure because of socially significant diseases (approximately 18 million people annually), followed by oncological diseases (9 million), diseases of the respiratory system (approximately 4 million) and diabetes (approximately 2 million).[7] As

practice demonstrates, the reduction of main risk factors could decrease mortality and morbidity of these diseases.

We have formulated a Concept for health risk factors that at present is within the foundations of chronic non-communicable diseases prophylactics in conformity with the National program for chronic non-communicable diseases prophylactics 2021-2025. It states that there are different classifications of risk factors. According to one of these, these are divided into preventable and nonpreventable (age, sex, heredity). To prophylactics, the first ones are essential. These are the factors related to social environment and people's behaviour. When interacting with genetic and other factors these result in the occurrence of risk biologic factors via which their participation in the development of chronic non-communicable diseases is realized. [9]

According to the data provided by the World Health Organization, smoking-related diseases cause the death of more than 8 million people annually. Over 7 million of the death cases are of present and former smokers and over 1,2 million – of nonsmokers exposed to passive smoking. [10]

Another risk factor is low physical activity. Numerous researches held in recent decades demonstrate that low physical activity is widespread in all the age

groups of our country's population and has large-scale consequences for public health. In the European region, it predefines 10-15% of total mortality (one million death cases annually) and 3,5% of the disease burden (9,7% combined with unhealthy diet) and has significant contribution in deterioration of population health status in our country. [2,4]

The main risk factors for malignant diseases are related to environmental factors and in particular its pollution with chemical compounds that get inside human organism via food, water or air, i.e. around 80% of ethiopathogenesis in people is related to impact of chemical cancerogenic ingredients. [3,5] Another main factor for malignant diseases is the insufficient intake of fruit and vegetables, high sugar and salt consumption in our country. It is related to around 14% of mortality as a result of gastrointestinal cancer, around 11% of mortality due to ischaemic cardiac disease and around 9% of mortality as a result of stroke worldwide. [1,6]

The objective of the research is to survey the lifestyle, consumption of fruit and vegetables and physical activity as risk factors for the occurrence and development of socially significant diseases of women and men aged 25-65.

2. Methodology

We have used documentary method for research of the accessible documentation, sociological method and graphic method for results' visualization. Via direct individual anonymous inquiry we have surveyed the opinion of 81 female and male smokers aged 25-65 about their lifestyle. The research was held in the period August - October 2023.

3. Results and discussion

Smoking is main behavioural factor of health risk and among the leading preventable reasons for the occurrence of socially significant diseases, death and disability. (figure 1)

Figure 1. How many cigarettes do you smoke daily?

Only 10 % of the inquired people smoke up to 20 cigarettes daily or one box. Many respondents (65%) smoke more than one box of cigarettes daily and this troublesome. Women smoke more than men. In the case of replies with over 30 cigarettes daily, the number is in males' favour. According to the European research

80% of those who consume tobacco live in countries with small or low income per capita and Bulgaria is no exception. Here comes the next logical question since lower age limit of adolescents when they decide to try their first cigarette gets lower and lower. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. What is the age you lit your first cigarette at?

Be it because of curiosity or in order to be fashionable, or because they were passive smokers, children try their first cigarette at ever decreasing age and then because of various reasons they keep on smoking (70% or nearly $\frac{3}{4}$ of all the inquired persons). Only $\frac{1}{4}$ of them

start their first cigarette aged 18 to 22. The share of those that decide to try something new like smoking is very low. Main factor for malignant diseases is not only smoking but unhealthy diet and in particular the insufficient consumption of fruit and vegetables. (figure 3)

Figure 3. Does your daily diet include sufficient quantity of fruit and vegetables?

Around 40% of the inquired persons do not consume sufficient quantity of fruit and vegetables on everyday basis and nearly as many do not consume fruit and vegetables at all. The respondents that partially or fully include sufficient quantities of fruit and vegetables in their menu are only $\frac{1}{4}$ of all which is quite insufficient so that we could summarize the group has a

healthy diet. This is another proof that fresh fruit and vegetables are not present in the menu of most people. Food habits in combination with low physical activity and lack of motion are serious risk factors for the occurrence of socially significant diseases. (figure 4)

Figure 4. How would you define your physical activity?

The low physical activity is quite widespread among inquired persons (36%), yet is slightly below the level of average high physical activity (38%), whereas average high physical activity means being active for health at least once weekly, high – twice weekly and very high – trice weekly whose share is lowest (9%). Yet this is hopeful result that states the inquired group takes care after its physical health and somewhat above 1/3 of them all are doing sports at least once weekly. The people more active in doing sports are aged between 25-50. The reasons behind low physical activity stated by the respondents are that in their dynamic daily life they either do not have the time or the desire for sports.

Conclusion:

The main goal of our healthcare system should be related to not allowing further deterioration of nation's health and creating the necessary prerequisites for its improvement.

Some of the significant risk factors that result in the occurrence and development of socially significant diseases are smoking cigarettes, unhealthy diet and low physical activity.

Health diet is a key aspect of prevention and one of the effective ways to cope with socially significant diseases. The impact onto one of the basic health determinants – nutrition throughout our life is prerequisite for healthy way of life with positive effect onto personal and public health in the long run.

One-third of the socially significant diseases could be prevented with effective approaches for smoking control and alcohol consumption, healthy diet and physical activity. In this light, positive impact could be related to increasing the number of school classes devoted to health culture and education in order to appeal for healthy behaviour, improvement of health literacy and awareness in the infant years which would result in

improvement of Bulgarian citizens' health status and longer healthier life.

We need to prepare programs for prevention and promotion of anti-risk behaviour of young people, health schools – seminars with teachers on psychohygienic, dietary and physical habits of children. Additionally, it is essential to elaborate adequate programs for chronically ill patients /with socially significant diseases/ implemented by general practitioners and specialists of outpatient medical care, in order to ensure cutting-edge and consistent treatment, disease control, as well as improvement of workability, life quality and duration of these patients. In this light, we need to prioritize financial resources of the National Health Insurance Fund in order to stimulate prophylactics and control of chronic diseases at outpatient care level.

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